

The Algorithm of Semi-Automatic Thai Spoonerism Words for Bi-Syllable

Nutthapat Kaewrattanapat, Wannarat Bunchongkien

Abstract—The purposes of this research are to study and develop the algorithm of Thai spoonerism words by semi-automatic computer programs, that is to say, in part of data input, syllables are already separated and in part of spoonerism, the developed algorithm is utilized, which can establish rules and mechanisms in Thai spoonerism words for bi-syllables by utilizing analysis in elements of the syllables, namely cluster consonant, vowel, intonation mark and final consonant. From the study, it is found that bi-syllable Thai spoonerism has 1 case of spoonerism mechanism, namely transposition in value of vowel, intonation mark and consonant of both 2 syllables but keeping consonant value and cluster word (if any).

From the study, the rules and mechanisms in Thai spoonerism word were applied to develop as Thai spoonerism word software, utilizing PHP program. the software was brought to conduct a performance test on software execution; it is found that the program performs bi-syllable Thai spoonerism correctly or 99% of all words used in the test and found faults on the program at 1% as the words obtained from spoonerism may not be spelling in conformity with Thai grammar and the answer in Thai spoonerism could be more than 1 answer.

Keywords—Algorithm, Spoonerism, Computational Linguistics.

I. INTRODUCTION

HUMANKIND uses language as the tool for communication in different forms corresponding to events or experience happened in daily life for negotiation, talking in several matters by verbal language or non-verbal language in order to express meaning for understanding correspondingly; therefore, language is an important factor for expressing meaning “what speaker wants to say” to listener for understanding correspondingly; moreover, nowadays, the evolution in language is changing according to social and cultural age, greatly affecting in language usage either in any form [4], [6].

Culture of Language could, therefore, be regarded as one kind of art affecting in communication [7]. The researcher perceived the beauty of pun in language usage; therefore, a design was conducted to demonstrate spoonerism by utilizing linguistic rules to support in spoonerism for creating knowledge, including functions and rules in spoonerism to obtain concrete and certain method in spoonerism as spoonerism is the art of word play having twisting between

Nutthapat Kaewrattanapat is Head of Information Management Program, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (e-mail: nutthapat.ke@ssru.ac.th).

Wannarat Bunchongkien is lecturer member of Information Management Program, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (e-mail: wannarat.bu@ssru.ac.th).

transposition of sound or syllables; this indicates that Thai language is always shifting and changing constantly, all of which are the trait of Thai people as the purpose of spoonerism is to use for playing for enjoyment and compete linguistic intelligence being regarded as a demonstration of linguistic ability [3].

The researcher envisioned the importance in Thai spoonerism play; thus, the study of Thai spoonerism was conducted by analyzing elements of syllables in each syllable, namely consonant, vowel, intonation mark and final consonant in order to find probability of spoonerism and establish rule and mechanism in Thai spoonerism for bi-syllable and store the knowledge related to Thai spoonerism in order to have the certain form. For the study of algorithm in spoonerism, the researcher collected the obtained knowledge from the study for conducting a computer-language algorithm structure by utilizing PHP language programing and word processing as the interested persons could bring it to study and develop in several fields further.

II. OBJECTIVE

The aim is to study a Thai spoonerism algorithm and establish rules or mechanisms in Semi-automatic Thai spoonerism for Bi-syllable.

III. HYPOTHESIS OF SPECIAL SUBJECTS

Rules and algorithm in developed method are able to conduct automatic Thai spoonerism correctly at 95%.

IV. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

- A. *To Obtain More Computational Linguistics Knowledge* and be able to bring such obtained knowledge to develop further in order to increase a performance in the program further.
- B. *To Obtain Forms of Rules and Mechanisms in Spoonerism* in order to be guidelines for applying with related subjects to be new guidelines in the study.
- C. *To Obtain System of the Linguistic Program for Application* from several subjects which is collected and analyzed until it generates new knowledge.
- D. *Can be Used to Analyze the Sentiment Analysis* in the future, which are needed in Thai language because of the spoonerism is a factor or effect the opinion of messages.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Spoonerism

The Royal Institute of Thailand (B.E.2546) gave the

definition of “spoonerism” as “a reversible word such as “Tok-Tee-It” (“ตก-ที-อีฐึ”, Falling bricks) to be “Tit-Tee-Ok” (“ติด-ที-อก”, Breast stuck) as spoonerism words.

B. Element of Thai Syllable

Syllable in Thai language has 3 important elements, including initial consonant + vowel sound+ intonation tone.

Initial consonant sound is such as a consonant which is pronounced before the other consonant; initial consonant can be single initial consonant or initial cluster consonant, for example Pāt and Prāt [1].

Vowel sound is such as a sound pronounced along with consonant swiftly, making initial consonant pronounced clearly; vowel can be short-sound single vowel, long-sound single vowel or diphthong mixed with any one of sound.

Intonation tone is such as high-pitch or low-pitch sound pronounced with vowel [5].

Elements of syllable have 3 important parts, namely initial consonant, vowel, intonation mark (having or not having a letter representing sound). PrayaUpakitSilapasarn (B.E.2533) explained the elements of syllable that it is created by compounding letter having 4 forms which could be summarized as follows [2], [8]:

- 1) Compounding 3 parts of letters, such as syllable generated from compounding of initial consonant + vowel + intonation mark, for example **มี**(Mī = Have), **นา** (Na = Field), **ห้า**(Ha = Five) , **ไร่** (Rai = Farm)etc.

Fig. 1 Compounding 3 parts of letters

- 2) Compounding 4 general parts of letters, such as syllable generated from compounding of initial consonant + vowel + final consonant + intonation mark, for example **ปลาย** (Phla = Elephant) and **งาม** (ngām = Beautiful) etc.

Fig. 2 Compounding 4 general parts of letters

- 3) Compounding 4 special parts, such as syllable generated from compounding of initial consonant + vowel + intonation mark + mute intonation mark, for example **เล่น**(Lē= Trick) , **สิงห์** (Sī = Lion), **เบียร์** (Beer = Beer) etc.

TABLE I
THAI SYLLABLE

Thai	English	Syllable
ไร่	Farm	Rai (Syllable)
ชาวนา	Farmer	Chāo-Rai (2-Syllables)
สหกรณ์	Cooperative	Sa-ha-kon (3-Syllables)
โรงพยาบาล	Hospital	Rōng-pha-yā-bān(4-Syllables)
นักศึกษาผู้ใหญ่	Adult Students	Nak-seuk-sā-phū-yai(5-Syllables)
ศูนย์สหกรณ์การเกษตร	Agricultural cooperative	Sa-ha-kon-kan-ka-sēt (6-Syllables)

Fig. 3 Compounding 4 special parts

- 4) Compounding 5 parts, such as syllable generated from compounding of initial consonant + vowel + final consonant + intonation mark + mute intonation mark, for example **ลักษณะ**(Lak = Image) , **พันธ์**(Khan = Group) and **จันทร์**(Jan = Moon) and etc.

Fig. 4 Compounding 5 parts

From the Table I, it demonstrates that syllable is the sound pronounced one time, whether having meaning or not; if it is pronounced 1 time, that means 1 syllable; if it is pronounced 2 times, that means 2 syllables according to Thai grammar.

VI. METHOD AND RESULT

A. Rules of Bi-Syllable Spoonerism

Probability of answers based on the theory of mathematical probability is bi-syllable word generating the probability as $2! = 2 \times 1 = 2$; therefore, the answer of the spoonerism can't generate results not more than 2 answers.

- 1) As for spoonerism of bi-syllables, the first syllable and second syllable must not have the same initial-sound consonant. If there are same initial-sound consonant, the spoonerism can't be conducted as the results will be only word transposition, for example **กาง-แกง** (Kāng-kēng), **โพง-พาง**(Phōng-phāng), **แสง-สี่**(Sāngsi) and etc.
- 2) For spoonerism of bi-syllable, the vowel form and final consonant must be the same sound, namely for example **รา-ชา**(Rā-chā), **ชม-รม** (Chom-rom)
- 3) Bi-syllable that when being pronounced as 3 syllables or compound word must use the rules of spoonerism for tri-syllable, and the data must be enter as reading word only because, if the rules of spoonerism for bi-syllables is used

intonation mark and final consonant), the program will transpose the value of the elements at the position of second letter to be transposed with other syllable, then display an output at monitor. Correctness of spoonerism word could be examined by inverting word needed to conduct spoonerism in order to obtain the answers in spoonerism with effectiveness and select a correct answer for application, further.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (<http://www.ssru.ac.th/>) to provide funding support to attend the dissemination of research on this and thank family, friends, colleagues and students in the field of Information Management for cooperation in research, all of you.

Finally, thanks to the Thai language which is our national language with its complicated grammars and structures that challenge the natural language processing.

REFERENCES

- [1] SutthiwongPongpaibool, "Principal of Thai Language," Thai Wattanapanich Press, Bangkok, 2001.
- [2] UdomWarosickadith, "Introduction to Thai Language," Ramkhamhaeng University Press, Bangkok Thailand, 2002.
- [3] Donald G. Mackay, "Spoonerisms: The structure of errors in the serial order of speech," University of California, Los Angeles, California, 1969.
- [4] Eugene A. Nida. "Morphology," The University of Michigan Press, 1947.
- [5] Heffner, R. M. S., "General Phonetics," University of Wisconsin Press, Madison, 1964.
- [6] Macneilage, P. F., "Personal communication," 1968.
- [7] Robbins, R. H., "The warden's wordplay: Toward a redefinition of the Spoonerism," *Dalhousie Rev.* 46, 1966, pp. 457-465.
- [8] Wells, F. L., "Linguistic Lapses," Science Press, New York, 1906.

Mr. Nutthapat Kaewrattanapat was born on 8, March 1983. He graduated Master's degree in Management Information System, King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok in 2005. He is a head and lecturer member of the Information Management Program, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. Contact: nutthapat.ke@ssru.ac.th and http://www.teacher.ssru.ac.th/nutthapat_ke/